

RECOVERY OF CERTAIN CATEGORIES OF EMPLOYEES SOME ISSUES RELATED.

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Abstract: *This thesis analyzes the part of the law and legal documents related to the employment of certain categories of employees, offers and conclusions aimed at the legal solution of errors and omissions in judicial practice in the process of their employment.*

Keywords: *law, judicial system, certain categories of employees, labor dispute, reinstatement, jurisdiction.*

After gaining independence, our country has entered a period of reforms for the benefit of man and his well-being. The guarantee of democratic rights and freedoms of the people, the supremacy of their interests is enshrined in the Constitution and laws.

Today, the judiciary is one of the most important components of a democratic state and plays a crucial role in the development of society. Improving the functioning of the judiciary in the new Uzbekistan, the formation of a truly independent judicial system that meets today's requirements is becoming an integral part of the new reforms.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev 2017 At a meeting with the judiciary on June 13, he said, "The main purpose of today's meeting is to think about the ongoing reforms in the judiciary, the shortcomings and problems in this area, ways to solve them, and to identify practical tasks. critical revision, radically improving its effectiveness, is becoming the most pressing task. Life itself forces it "[1]. the judicial system has been restructured to be fair, popular, able to fully protect the interests of citizens, and to solve their problems in a timely manner.

In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-6034 of July 24, 2020 "On additional measures to further improve the work of courts and increase the efficiency of justice" stipulates the adoption of a new version of the Law "On Courts" The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Courts" was adopted in a new edition. Currently, this law

serves to ensure the independence of the judiciary and increase the efficiency of justice.

Despite the large-scale reforms being carried out in the judiciary today, some laws and by-laws are being ignored in the adoption process. This, in turn, leads to confusion in the process of resolving disputes between labor relations and ensuring the execution of court documents. In particular, with the participation of certain categories of employees, it is difficult to find an impartial solution to emerging labor disputes related to employment.

For example, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017 The Regulation "On the Procedure for Service in the Internal Affairs Bodies" approved by Resolution No. PD-3413 of 29 November includes norms on recruitment and dismissal of employees to the internal affairs bodies. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional organizational measures to further improve the activities of law enforcement agencies in the field of public safety and the fight against crime" dated April 2, 2021 A number of amendments and additions were made to Resolution PD-3413 by Resolution PD-5050.

Paragraph 155 of this Resolution was amended to read as follows: "Paragraph 144 (l) of this Regulation on the basis of the entry into force of the decision on restoration or the decision of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Rehabilitation of persons dismissed from the service of the internal affairs bodies on all other grounds shall be carried out by the decision of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. [2]

If referred to in Article 144 of the Statute, the law enforcement agencies

It can be seen that employees can be dismissed on a total of 15 grounds, from sub-paragraph "a" to sub-paragraph "p". According to the above amendments, an employee can intervene in court and the employee can go to court only if the employee is dismissed under subparagraph "l" of paragraph 144 of the Statute, and then this argument is found unfounded. If the remaining 14 reasons (for example, incompetence, gross misconduct, illness, actions that tarnish the image of the police) are dismissed and the employer unfairly dismisses the employee, in such cases, reinstatement is carried out only by the decision of the Minister of Internal Affairs. increase was noted as the norm. This norm is a restriction of the employee's right to apply to the court to restore his violated rights in case of unjust dismissal under other circumstances. After all, Article

44 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "Everyone is guaranteed the right to judicial protection of their rights and freedoms, the right to appeal to the courts against illegal actions of state bodies, officials, public associations".[3]

Also of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan Article 18 stipulates that "the nature of the regulation of the work of civil servants shall be determined by law".[4]

The process of analysis shows that the above Regulation and amendments to it are legally contrary to both the Constitution and the Labor Code. This not only creates great obstacles for citizens to protect their rights and legitimate interests, but also leads to different approaches to issues considered and resolved by the court, and an increase in the workload of the judiciary as a result of repeated and repeated consideration of appeals. For example, only on February 16, 2013, the citizen A., who was dismissed from the system of internal affairs, filed a petition for reinstatement as a plaintiff. On December 17 and May 5, 2021, the Judicial Board for Civil Cases of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan reviewed the case again and again, and as a result of the court proceedings, the former employee was reinstated. Many such cases related to the reinstatement of former employees can be observed in court practice.

In summary, there are differences between laws and regulations that allow for different approaches to resolving labor disputes involving certain categories of military personnel or employees, and that these disputes are reviewed over and over again at different stages of the court process. Despite the fact that the application submitte. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.

This means that in the process of reviewing employment disputes related to employment by certain categories of employees, first of all, the existing laws and legal documents should be thoroughly studied by judges, as well as the issue of jurisdiction should be taken seriously. The effect of this is to prevent the recurrence of disputes, to protect the rights and freedoms of the plaintiff, to pursue his legitimate interests.

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